

SEN4AGRINET: A HARMONIZED MULTI-COUNTRY, MULTI-TEMPORAL BENCHMARK DATASET FOR AGRICULTURAL EARTH OBSERVATION MACHINE LEARNING APPLICATIONS

Dimitris Sykas⁽¹⁾, Ioannis Papoutsis⁽¹⁾, Dimitrios Zografakis⁽¹⁾

National Observatory of Athens, ⁽¹⁾dimisyk@noa.gr

ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a one of its kind labeled Earth Observation based benchmark dataset, Sen4AgriNet, for agricultural applications in Europe. The dataset is labeled using farmer declarations for the period 2016-2020, available as open data only very recently. The Sen4AgriNet contains 42.5 million parcels hence is significantly larger than the existing archives and is tailored to be used as a training source in the context of deep learning. It consists of two sub-datasets: Object Aggregated Dataset (OAD) and Patches Assembled Dataset (PAD). OAD dataset capitalizes zonal statistics of each parcel, thus creating a powerful label-to-features instance for classification algorithms. On the other hand, PAD structure generalizes the classification problem to parcel extraction and semantic segmentation and labeling. Key advantages from other similar datasets are the inclusion of all bands, multi-country and multi-year time span, and standardization of the crop type taxonomy across Europe. Finally, we showcase the potential of Sen4AgriNet through machine learning experiments.

Index Terms— benchmark satellite dataset, crop type classification, deep learning, crop harmonization taxonomy

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the availability of spectrally, temporally and spatially standardized satellite imagery products like Copernicus Sentinel 1 & 2 and NASA's Landsat program have enabled the consistent and robust monitoring of agricultural activities. The abundance of data combined with the advances of machine learning techniques open the way to better understand the complex agricultural ecosystems and generate know-how to support smart farming, Common Agriculture Policy - CAP implementation, and agricultural insurance.

Major bottleneck to reach these goals is the availability of extensive and standardized ground truth labels. However, EU countries, due to the CAP regulations, have developed a process to gather such ground truth data directly from the farmer's declarations. The LPIS (Land Parcel Identification System) [1] are the systems that record the declarations in a consistent country-wise way. Access to farmer declarations have been restricted for several years, and this information was mainly preserved by the EU Agricultural Paying

Agencies. However, since 2019 and for the first time, these datasets are gradually becoming open (e.g. France, Catalonia, Estonia, Croatia, Slovenia, Slovakia, and Luxemburg). This is a significant opportunity for the Earth Observation community to effectively exploit this new information, treating it effectively as ground truth data. In this work we tap onto this opportunity to create a benchmark dataset for Artificial Intelligence (AI) EO-based applications.

The combination of LPIS, satellite monitoring and machine learning (ML) techniques can be used to address several different AI problems: a) crop type classification, b) parcel extraction, c) parcel counting, d) semantic segmentation and labeling.

Although this combination holds great potential, several challenges need to be solved first. Each EU country has its own LPIS system tailored to its local/national agricultural practices, which incorporates a different crop categorization taxonomy in the local language. Additionally, parcels are recorded in the corresponding national cartographic projection. The non-standardization of the labels, prohibits the training of deep learning models that can generalize spatially and temporally.

In this paper we present a one of its kind benchmark dataset (Sen4AgriNet), with the following characteristics: a) it is pixel based, b) it is multi-temporal to capture the crop phenology, c) it is multi-annual to test the temporal generalization potential, d) it spans geographically to several EU countries to test the spatial generalization potential, and e) it is modular in the context that the dataset can be expanded in a straightforward way to use additional sensor and non-EO data, such as meteorological data, and enlarged with parcels from more EU countries.

The initial version of Sen4AgriNet consists of approximately 225,000 5-year multitemporal Sentinel-2 patches coregistered with open LPIS data for regions in Spain and France with a total size of 10TB. On top of the dataset, we have developed a series of functions such as spatio-temporal aggregations, to transform the original dataset according to the different AI problems one may wish to address (classification, segmentation, etc.). The dataset generation code and the basic functions will be made available through our github repository.

This paper is structured as follows: first we review existing datasets in remote sensing tailored for ML applications. We

then introduce a newly developed taxonomy to use as a universal dictionary of crop labels. We proceed to present the unique characteristics of the Sen4AgriNet dataset and finally we include some preliminary ML results for crop classification using this dataset.

2. REMOTE SENSING DATASETS FOR ML APPLICATIONS

The idea of creating benchmark datasets for remote sensing AI applications has recently gained traction in the community. Indeed, a few datasets already exist that combine labeled (not LPIS) data with satellite images. BigEarthNet [2] is a large-scale Sentinel-2 benchmark archive. BigEarthNet was constructed using, 125 Sentinel-2 tiles acquired between June 2017 and May 2018 over 10 European countries. All the tiles were atmospherically corrected using the sen2cor [3] tool from the European Space Agency. The tiles were divided into 590,326 non-overlapping image patches. Each image patch was annotated by the multiple land-cover classes (i.e., multi-labels) that were provided from the CORINE Land Cover database of the year 2018 (CLC 2018).

Eurosat [4] is a dataset based on Sentinel-2 satellite images covering 13 spectral bands and consisting out of 10 land cover classes with in total 27,000 labeled and georeferenced images. Similar to BigEarthNet, each patch contains tag(s) of the contained classes.

The so2Sat [5] LCZ42 consists of local climate zone (LCZ) labels of about half a million Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 image patches in 42 urban agglomerations (plus 10 additional smaller areas) across the globe. This dataset was labeled by 15 domain experts following a carefully designed labeling work flow and evaluation process over a period of six months.

The “CV4A Kenya Crop Type Competition” [6] is an indicative example on how to combine satellite temporal images with crop types. This dataset exploits both the temporal nature of satellite images and the spatial distribution (parcels) of crop types. This dataset has three shortcomings: 1) it consists of a small number of parcels, 2) there is low variability of different crop types, 3) it spans along one year and does not contain multi-annual data.

The BreizhCrop dataset is a new benchmark dataset for the supervised classification of field crops from satellite time series. In the work of [7], the authors combined labeled data and Sentinel-2 top-of-atmosphere as well as bottom-of-atmosphere time series in the region of Brittany, north-east France, spanning throughout 2017. The approach is parcel based, i.e. for each parcel the authors estimate the spatially aggregated Sentinel-2 reflectances for each available acquisition in 2017.

Most the related existing datasets do not handle the temporal aspect of satellite images, while most of them focus on annotating tags instead of masks, which constrains the usage of the dataset in simple classification scenarios ([Table 1](#)–[Table 4](#)). Image segmentation, object detection, etc. are deep learning problems that cannot be addressed with this kind of

configuration. Also, not including the temporal aspect of the satellite images, restricts deep learning models from learning the temporal/seasonal dynamics of the classes. Although, land cover types and urban structures do not usually exhibit seasonality in their spectral signatures (only the temporal aspect could be considered as change detection), crop types do so, making essential the exploitation of the temporal aspect of the images.

In addition, different crop types at different geographic areas present a variable spectral and spatial behavior. Phenology stages, different seeding dates, varying meteorological conditions are just a few parameters that make the spatio-temporal aspect of the data essential in order to perform efficient, accurate and robust classifiers. We aspire that we address this with Sen4AgriNet dataset.

Table 1. List of existing RS datasets for ML applications

<i>Dataset</i>	<i>Object vs pixel</i>	<i>Spatial / temporal coverage</i>	<i>RS application</i>	<i>No of labels</i>
BigEarthNet	Pixel	EU countries /no	Land cover	590k
Eurosat	Pixel	EU countries/ no	Land cover	27k
so2Sat	Pixel	Global	Urban mapping	500k
CV4A	Object	Local in Kenya/ 1Y	Agriculture	4k
BreizhCrop	Object	Local in France/1Y	Agriculture	610k
Sen4AgriNet	Object & pixel	EU countries /multi-temporal, multi-annual	Agriculture	42000K

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Harmonized crop type taxonomy

The Sen4AgriNet adopts a custom extended version of FAO Indicative Crop Classification (ICC) [10], in order to create a universally applicable crop label nomenclature. We created this version in order to include some major land use classes from Corine Land Cover (CLC), and a few additional classes to complete the semantic concept (“fallow land” sub-class, “baren land” sub-class and “no data available” sub-class). CLC classes related to agriculture and forestry were not included, since they are properly and in detail covered by FAO ICC. Fallow land, baren land and no data available were separately added. FAO ICC has 4 hierarchies (Group, Class, Sub-Class, Order), with corresponding numeric ordering. From the 160+ entities in the hierarchy, the fourth one (Order) contained only 15 entities. In order to reduce the complexity of any future classification attempts and different label groupings, the “Order” level was removed by upgrading the corresponding entities to “Sub-Class” level and removing their parent “Sub-Class”.

The non-agriculture related classes were added in this crop classification scheme, since agricultural parcels co-exist with other unrelated classes. Adopting this custom FAO/CLC crop classification scheme to create Sen4AgriNet, provides the following benefits:

1. Single language (English) and naming for all classes across all participating countries
2. Normalization of classes among different datasets

Figure 1. Summary of the modified FAO ICC Crop Classification Scheme - Group and Class levels of hierarchy

- Hierarchical classes. Depending on the application used different levels of classes can be used
- Additional non-agricultural classes to model recorded signals to support agricultural applications

The presented custom FAO/CLC classification scheme has a total of 9 groups, 158 classes and sub-classes. The 151 classes/sub-classes are crop related, 4 are some major CLC classes (as sub-classes in this hierarchy), 2 are the fallow and barren lands, and 1 is the no data sub-class.

3.2. Land Parcel Identification Systems

Every LPIS dataset that is used to generate Sen4AgriNet, is firstly semantically normalized to the FAO ICC crop classification scheme. This is a manual procedure that is performed on every dataset containing farmer declarations that is available on a free and open basis. The current version of Sen4AgriNet contains:

- The LPIS data for the region of Catalonia are provided by the “Agricultura, Ramaderia, Pesca i Alimentació” with an Open Data Commons Attribution License from 2016 – 2020 [8]. Total of 2.5M parcels.
- France LPIS data is provided by the French Paying Agency with an Open Data Commons Attribution License from 2016 – 2019 [9]. Total of 40M parcels.

3.3. Dataset Structure

Sen4AgriNet is composed of two sub-datasets: Object Aggregated Dataset (OAD) and Patches Assembled Dataset (PAD). A processing pipeline was built in order to generate the PAD part of Sen4AgriNet. The OAD part is built on top of the PAD by aggregating to the parcel level. The processing is Sentinel-2 tile oriented per year. For each of the 55 tiles where LPIS data are available, all Sentinel-2 images L1C with less than 10% cloud cover were downloaded and split into patches. One tile is split into 900 patches. Each patch contains 366 by 366 pixels for the 10-meter bands, 183 by 183 for the 20-meter bands and 61 by 61 for the 60-meter bands. For each patch the corresponding 366 by 366 LPIS

with the Sen4AgriNet taxonomy applied was rasterized to match the specific pixels in that patch. Using this formulation each patch includes a total of $13 \cdot n_{\text{time}} + 2$ geotiff files. Thirteen geotiff files (Sentinel-2 bands) for the spectral measurements for n_{time} time acquisitions (depending on the region n varies from 30 to 50 timestamps for one year) and 2 geotiff files for the parcel ids and their corresponding crop type labels. Thus, the size of the resulting dataset is huge. A single Sentinel-2 tile stack that is transformed into patches for one-year span, results in ~ 900 patches in total and has volume ~ 40 GBs.

France’s and Catalonia’s parcels are mainly present in 55 Sentinel-2 tiles ([Figure 2: France and Catalonia \(Spain\) LPIS dataset overlaid with Sentinel-2 tiles](#)~~Figure 2: France and Catalonia LPIS dataset overlaid with Sentinel-2 tiles~~). The total size of the Sen4AgriNet dataset is estimated to be 10 TB for the 2016-2020 time span, which corresponds to a total of 225,000 number of patches. Due to the challenging size of the dataset, Sen4AgriNet will be made available for free during 2021.

Being able to train a deep network on this size of dataset, requires significant computational power, thus we also introduce a parcel aggregated version of the Sen4AgriNet dataset. The parcel aggregated version is a csv file that includes in rows each parcel per available time acquisition spatially aggregated per band. The spatial aggregation functions that are used are: mean, standard deviation, and skewness. This configuration results to a csv file that have $n_{\text{time}} \cdot n_{\text{parcels}}$ rows and 42 columns (3 aggregation functions * 13 spectral bands + time acquisition + crop type code + parcel id).

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS FOR CROP CLASSIFICATION

In this paper the experiments are focused on the Catalonia’s part of the Sen4AgriNet dataset for the year 2020. The goal of these experiments is the crop type classification (OAD)

and crop land mapping (PAD). The experiments are divided into two main categories according to the version of the Sen4AgriNet dataset used: i.) PAD, ii.) OAD. Parcels of the same category may develop different behaviors for a number of factors (location, soil, etc.). PAD dataset, promotes the idea of spatial variability of the different crop types. Having information on the geometry of the parcels, crop land mapping is translated to a binary classification problem. OAD dataset, promotes the idea of extracting zonal statistics (mean, std, skewness, etc.) for each unique parcel. Having access to the wider category (crop type) and time captured (timestamp) we are able to aggregate statistics into time-bins. This method serves as an initial benchmark for later implementations.

4.1. Sen4AgriNet – PAD Experiment

PAD is trained using Detectron2’s API, which offers support for custom datasets in a COCO-like formatting, therefore our approach consists of treating each parcel (geographic coords to pixel coords) as an annotation to its corresponding patch. The semantic segmentation part of the Detectron2 is used to binary classify the pixels of the patches as crop land or not. Every patch has a static object representation in time domain, but image values will differ. Training and fine tuning take part in patch level, as treating each patch as an image makes more sense and ensures dataset tampering will not be an issue. Training was performed in 900 patches with R1010-FPN backbone. Results seem promising, given that the training was performed in fraction of the dataset.

4.2. Sen4AgriNet – OAD Experiment

In the second experiment standard sequential neural network architecture is used. A fully connected deep neural network (NN/MLP) (4 layers, 512, 256, 128, 64 nodes each layer), which ignores time altogether and a more sophisticated network using LSTM layers instead of a dense NN. In both cases the last layers is the standard fully connected layer having a SoftMax activation function. A custom generator was built to arrange the Sen4AgriNet parcel aggregated dataset to tensors to properly input the LSTM layer. The tensor has dimensions [batch size, temporal aggregated bins, features (per band statistics)]. The temporal aggregated bins is monthly (12) and batch size is configured at 1024. Each slice of the tensor [i, *, *] corresponds to a single parcel.

PAD	78.08%			
OAD	MLP	69.43%	LSTM	72.95%

For OAD, 27 unique classes existed. The metric in all cases is the overall classification.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The Sen4AgriNet dataset has been introduced in this paper. We tackle the lack of label harmonization by proposing a FAO inspired nomenclature. We also make available the first Sentinel-2 multi-temporal, multi-country labeled dataset exploiting the recently openly available LPIS data. Sen4AgriNet has already 225,000 patches with corresponding crop type maps, providing an excellent asset to benchmark and develop DL approaches for the remote sensing agriculture domain. Our future work includes, further

refining Sen4AgriNet with Sentinel-1 data and implementing enhanced cloud filtering for optical images.

Figure 2: France and Catalonia (Spain) LPIS dataset overlaid with Sentinel-2 tiles

8. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 883284

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